

SOCIAL INCLUSION OF EX-PRISONERS FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF SOCIETY

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ABSTRACT

The research theme of this article is 'social inclusion of ex-prisoners from the perspective of Society'. We are opting for the line of research 'State, educational policies and social change'. Research on this subject is little disseminated and very little explored in its essence. Even though civil public rights have been universalized, through the promulgation of the 1988 Federal Constitution, the social inclusion of individuals whose conditions of freedom have been temporarily interrupted is a subject considered taboo for civil society. Its scientific relevance lies in the fact that it brings to the academic discussion an entire apparatus of understanding and interpretation on how the exclusion of these individuals is carried out. Its social relevance is present in the fact that this is a contemporary problem, exalted by the conditions set out in documents relating to human rights, considering the immense category of individuals deprived of their freedom today. This is a bibliographical, factual research, based on classic authors and the author's personal experience, based on his teaching practice in the area. The social inclusion of ex-prisoners is a problem of social and governmental public policy; because, if on the one hand there is a lack of support from society in rehabilitating and accepting the individual who violated legal dictates, breaking social norms, on the other hand there is a lack of affirmative policies regarding jobs, housing, reception and social security guarantees on the part of society from the State to these individuals until they can relocate and obtain a dignified occupation; in other words, when leaving the prison space, they find themselves at the mercy of their own luck or misfortune and, most of the time, to achieve a miserable condition of human survival they return to crime.

Keywords: Social inclusion of ex-prisoners; Public policy; Human rights; Delinquency.

INTRODUCTION

The scientific approach theme of this article is the social inclusion of ex-prisoners from the perspective of civil society. It is following the line of thought 'State, educational policies and social change'. Research on this subject is little disseminated and very little explored in its essence. Even though civil public rights have been universalized in Brazil, through the

promulgation of the 1988 Federal Constitution, the social inclusion of individuals whose conditions of freedom have been temporarily interrupted is still a *taboo subject* for civil society.

From the above, a question arises that refers to what to do with this individual after being declared free by the courts, that is, once he has fulfilled his sentence decreed by the State, upon being judged by his peers. Denying its existence, as it has been done, is impractical and if such an attitude is carried out, this is already a social condemnation for it to live on the margins and have delinquency as its final destination.

This is a subject of utmost relevance, given that Brazilian legislation allows a maximum period of imprisonment, under a regime deprived of the condition of liberty, of 30 (thirty) years and Brazilian life expectancy already exceeds 70 (seventy) years of age. age, taking into account that the average age of the prison population varies between 18 (eighteen) and 24 (twenty-four) years. Considering that an individual is sentenced to the maximum sentence, they will still leave the detention center accommodations in full physical strength and in perfect mental condition, considering the Brazilian forensic psychiatric evaluation system.

It is inferred that the social inclusion of ex-prisoners is a problem of social and governmental public policy; because, if on the one hand there is a lack of support from society in rehabilitating and accepting the individual who violated the *legal dictates*, breaking social norms, on the other hand there is a lack of affirmative policies regarding jobs, housing, reception and social security guarantees on the part of society. from the State to these individuals until they can relocate and obtain a dignified occupation; in other words, when leaving the prison space, they find themselves at the mercy of their own luck or misfortune and, most of the time, to achieve a miserable condition of human survival they return to crime.

Social inclusion is a subject of wide discussion in the media and in formal academic circles. These are issues related to ways of offering support and dignity to individuals who have been removed from public life for breaking the law. The inclusion of ex-prisoners is a subject that, at first glance, everyone avoids discussing and, in this way, the issue is considered non-existent, or as if not talking about the problem consummates its non-existence. Given the above, the research question unfolds around the following question: how does society understand the social inclusion of ex-convicts?

The inclusion of ex-prisoners is still a little explored subject, despite being widely discussed in academic circles. There is no common conception that serves as a basis for other questions or for the formulation of public policies in this field. Therefore, the present work intends to bring to light society's perception regarding the social inclusion of ex-convicts.

Upon leaving prison, the individual's first vision is to look for a job and, most of the time, what they get is some underemployment. Considering that they have few employment opportunities and formal jobs left, this research aims to identify how the social inclusion of ex-prisoners occurs from the perspective of the formal job market and understand how society understands the precepts of Social inclusion and exclusion is always a factor that arouses curiosity and promotes debate and reflection. Therefore, the investigation in question aims to analyze the social representation of the social inclusion of ex-detainees.

In Brazil, there are so-called social assistance reference centers and even the Ministry of Human Rights, bodies responsible for dealing with the omitted chaos of exclusion; however, at no time is any work carried out involving the promotion and discussion about the inclusion of individuals who were deprived of their temporary freedom and were released. Faced with this question, the research intends to investigate how local civil society relativizes its proposals for support in the re-insertion of ex-prisoners in their environment. The objective of this study is to encourage public authorities to create public policies aimed at the inclusion of ex-convicts, in order to restore their integrity and full citizenship.

Social inclusion processes always cover inter and transdisciplinary fields, in addition to subjective values. When promoting inclusion, one must try to be aware of the risk of falling short of the offer and [or] promoting an inclusion in reverse or a sublime exclusion. Within this approach, the general objective of this investigation is to verify how civil society perceives and conceives the social inclusion of local ex-prisoners. Exclusion is a factor that is difficult to interpret because the excluded person feels excluded from themselves and transfers this feeling to others. He sees his feeling of non-acceptance of himself reflected in the other's eyes. Therefore, his refusal to accept his image reflected in the mirror, what he sees expressed in the eyes of the observer [*intrinsic*] of the mirror is transmitted to his extrinsic reality. In this way, the problem of inclusion/exclusion does not occur in a one-way street, it is a two-way street, where the subject has to accept himself as an actor of his own destiny. To include is to accept, and this means that the subject has to accept himself to transmit this personal security to his companions.

THE PROBLEM ABOUT THE SOCIAL INCLUSION OF EX-PRISONERS

Social inclusion presupposes the integration or reintegration into society of those who, for various reasons, find themselves on the margins of a context of minimal quality of life. The social inclusion of ex-detainees is still something that receives very little support from the

population and the government. Once he has served his sentence and considering the low degree of effectiveness of the Brazilian prison system in re-educating criminals, the ex-convict is, for the free society, if society reintegrates him immediately, runs the risk of having, within their homes and/or businesses, someone very susceptible to committing new crimes; However, if society does not reinstate him immediately, he will be certain that this person will commit new crimes. However, society needs to understand that this will only be viable if reintegration begins on the first day of serving the sentence. Otherwise, there is no point in expecting a prisoner to be ready to live in society just because he served his time behind bars, where there was the most complete environment of violence and injustice:

The International System for the Protection of Human Rights constitutes the greatest legacy of the so-called “era of Rights”, which has allowed the internationalization of human rights and the humanization of contemporary international law (...). If the Second World War symbolized the rupture in relation to human rights, the Post-War era meant the hope of rebuilding these same rights. It is in this scenario that the effort to rebuild human rights is designed, as a paradigm and ethical reference to guide the contemporary international order. Thus, the great criticism and repudiation of the positivist conception of a legal system indifferent to ethical values, confined to a merely formal perspective, is manifested - considering that Nazism and fascism rose to power within the framework of legality and promoted barbarity in the name of the law (PIOVESAN and SOUZA, 2006, p. 37).

In this way, understood as a space for learning to be and learning to live together, society is also a space where the individual can and should exercise protagonism, acting effectively in it, presenting proposals, promoting discussions that concern the social life of interest to society. community, participating in organizations such as guilds or other work groups of interest capable of contributing to the construction or strengthening of the identity of themselves and their peers. But society, with its mores and its culture already crystallized on Judeo-Christian bases, does not allow itself to accept that this protagonist is someone who transgressed its rules. Which makes it a place that rejects what it considers unworthy of its political coexistence.

Papin (2012) argues that,

Upon returning to society, ex-detainees are evicted after years of incarceration without, during this period, the State taking measures to ensure that these people become capable of facing the new challenge. Difficulty finding work, abandonment of the family, need to adapt to judgments and unfounded opinions through moral blindness. The prejudice of society as a whole, including States and their rulers, means that ex-detainees are treated as marginalized (PAPINI, 2012, p. 15).

Man only feels like a man [*human being, in the strict sense of the term*] within a complex social group. Complex, because it is through developments that your personality solidifies and

consolidates. The child at birth even fears his own father, who *initially* appears to him as a hostile figure and only after long relationships do the edges tend to diminish. This is to get a brief idea of the tangle that makes up the human soul and the relationships that involve the construction of personality and its psychosocial nuances.

The force that absolutist power exerts on the human mind, combined with the natural and unequal conditions of social development, is a dish full of opportunities for totalitarian regimes to prevail and create roots that are difficult to eradicate. In this context, revolutionaries emerge who are considered by two groups as anarchists: “the dominant class and the miserable class”. The revolutionary class is the one in the middle, which is generally the intellectual elite. They are freethinkers, idealists and men of vision. They are not well regarded by the ruling class, because they denounce the abuses to which they subject the less favored. They are not loved by the poor because, since they arouse the anger of those in power, these rebels can deprive them of their meager rights.

Man reacts according to the environment in which he is inserted... Some children, nowadays, when they are born, the first lesson they must learn is how to escape from their parents so as not to be devoured... Man is not a It is a product of the environment in which he lives, however, that this environment will have a strong influence on his psychology, his *modus vivendis*, there is no refutable doubt.

Playfair & Sington (1969) argue that,

Prison is a punishment; With the exception of the death penalty, it is the most severe sanction provided by criminal legislation. And punishment, unless the dictionary lies, is retribution. These perhaps evident facts are emphatically proclaimed by us because there is, among contemporary penologists, a tendency to attenuate the first of them in order to deny the second. However, no one can get rid of something inconvenient simply by saying it doesn't exist. Whether retribution is a euphemism for revenge or an expression of righteous disapproval is feasible under the circumstances and always subject to doubt. (PLAYFAIR & SINGTON, 1969, p. 15)

The principles of identity, diversity and autonomy redefine the relationship to be maintained between the systems of exclusion and inclusion adopted by society. This proposal should not be understood as an absence or omission of the State. On the contrary, identity and autonomy are exercised in the context constituted by general guidelines for action and advice on the implementation of social inclusion policies, which requires the systems that make up civil society (federal, state or municipal), so that autonomy does not constitute neglect or abandonment, the definition of guidelines for an inclusion policy that reflects the needs and

demands of the system, in line with the National Guidelines and the structuring of mechanisms for supervision/advisory, monitoring and evaluation of the results of the performance of same.

According to Alfred Adler [*sd*] cited by Mullahay (1975),

All failures – neurotics, psychotics, criminals, drunks, difficult children, suicides, perverts and prostitutes – are failures because they lack the feeling of human solidarity and social interest. They address the problems of occupation, friendship and sex, without the confidence that they can be solved through cooperation. The meaning they give to life is a particular meaning: no one else benefits from the achievement of their own goals and their interests do not exceed the limits of their persons. The objective of success boils down to an objective of mere fictitious superiority and their triumphs only have meaning for them (MULAHAY, 1975, p. 152)

These invisible figures become islands that wander through the limbo of life; They very soon taste the bitter taste of exclusion from everything that enchants them and cling, as the ultimate end of hope and way of survival, to any piece of misery that human life can offer them. Hatred, mockery, pain, disaffection, contempt are the only tangible feelings that many have known throughout their entire existence, because these were the only feelings with which they had real contact. And to be known and re-recognized, they become figures holding what most haunts humanity: 'the reflection of their self'; They expose what everyone desperately tries to hide, even from themselves.

We live in a contemporary world marked by an arbitrary society, which excludes the importance of interpersonal relationships, which places individual desires, past experiences and the lack of future projection as insignificant. There is a lack of a dialectic of social development that promotes organic growth of the being as author and actor of its history within a social context. While society preaches a relativist discourse marked by two truths, none of which are intended to promote adulthood, it ends up causing consensual rape among its clientele. It causes what Gramsci (1996) called sublime revenge.

For this theorist,

Sublime revenge can also be called “falsification of tables of value”, “alteration of meaning”, “transvaluation”, as there is the idea of changing values from “bad” to positive “good” value, but such change is derived of a lie, even if it is unconscious. This lie is called “organic lying”. “The organic lie is constituted wherever it comes to the minds of men except what serves their 'interests', or any placement of impulsive attention”. So, consciousness is the basis of values, however, this arises from how they are apprehended by judgments about values, whether through falsification or not. The falsification of tables of value or alteration of meaning or even transvaluation results in resentment and moral judgment of value. From ethics in modernity, different morals began to exist, leading to ethical and moral relativism. However, many of the relativist morals were not considered useful, even so, this moral was

intrinsically linked to the idea of usefulness for a community. Scheler exemplifies the issue of “theft”. He says that relativists may view theft in a given community as a small crime, while theft for the ancients, especially the Germans, was seen as a major crime. Surely you have heard the saying “what is ethical or moral for me may not be for you”. This is relativism. Even though theft is seen as a small crime by relativists, they claim that the fundamental value is the same (GRAMSCI, 1996, p. 78).

When Gramsci presents the issue of sublime revenge, one can understand the condition of a sublimated aversion, disguised under the demagogy of security and the possibility of new transgression of ethical limits by ex-convicts. But, all this is, once again, relative, because criminals of all types continue to plague society without citizens showing aversion to them and their persistent, commonplace and persistent crimes. Of all this, the object of judgment is the fact that some are captured and placed in quarantine, in order to atone for the evil that plagues the entire society and this simple condition of disgrace already condemns them forever, in the eyes of from everyone else.

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights, in an attempt to inhibit conflict situations in which difference was treated as a target object triggering one of the most violent wars and social exclusion of a people, leading them to darkness, marginalization and death. , has its precept of legal equality reiterated by the Brazilian Constitution of 1988, which aims, with this guarantee, to maintain peace and avoid unnecessary conflicts.

In its article 1, section III, it deals with the condition of dignity of the human person, as a fundamental clause that must be based on the precepts of preserving life, above all. Equality is also expressly provided for among fundamental rights and guarantees, in article 5th of the 1988 Federal Constitution, as *in verbis* :

Art. 5th. Everyone is equal before the law, without distinction of any kind, guaranteeing Brazilians and foreigners residing in the country the inviolability of the right to life, freedom, equality, security and property [...]. (BRASIL, 1988, p. 15).

formal equality and substantial equality are foreseen , which allows us to conclude that in the Democratic State of Law both one and the other receive the same importance. There are, therefore, several expressions expressed when dealing with the assumptions for confronting racial inequalities in Brazil. Interpretative obstacles must be overcome around the *Principle of Equality* – in the implementation of true positive commands to correct asymmetries for inequalities in the country.

If, initially, human rights advocate general protection based on the liberal principle of equality, with the evolution of urban societies, especially from the second half of the 20th

century, the idea of diversity gains importance. In fact, it is observed that some sectors have historically faced obstacles in their access to material and immaterial goods. Therefore, there is a leveling of conditions legitimized by the premise of formal equality, not recognizing the particularities and peculiarities that surround the factual circumstances of poverty and discrimination.

In this way, emphasizes Piovesan, who

It is necessary to specify the subject of law, which is seen in its peculiarity and particularity. From this perspective, certain subjects of rights or certain violations of rights require a specific and differentiated response. In this scenario, women, children, the Afro-descendant population, migrants, people with disabilities, among other vulnerable categories, must be seen in the specificities and peculiarities of their social condition. Alongside the right to equality, the right to difference emerges as a fundamental right (PIOVESAN, 2009, p. 38).

The issue of difference and identity is a complex topic, because society tends to make everyone equal so that it can govern under abstract laws, the aim of which is to create a controllable environment. When diversity is allowed, there is a need for laws that adapt to this way of thinking and being, which makes the government more difficult to maintain. In this process, exclusion becomes an element that allows the maintenance of governance and social balance, despite it appearing otherwise. The logic of the exclusion/inclusion process follows precepts that are not very clear to society and are much more directed towards the interests of maintaining citizens' security control.

DISCUSSIONS ABOUT DIFFERENCE AND IDENTITY

According to Borges (2010), coexistence with difference and the different, provided by school, is also important for the perception that being different is not a problem; it is a peculiarity of the human race; It is therefore up to the school not to label the student as weak but as different and to highlight that the difference only exists in the social environment, because without the other to compare, there is no way to make measurements, valuations and the like. This coexistence contributes, at the same time, to the perception that it is not necessary to always be the same way: people change, build new values, assume new attitudes, develop new relationships. Differences also represent the possibility of seeing yourself in others and being able to clearly state: I am like this, I feel like this, I express my feelings like this and I think like this; He is different from me, he thinks differently, he feels and expresses his feelings differently.

Identity is something that is formed through constant coexistence. Difference is what is considered as not belonging to the given sphere. Both live in the field of historical struggles, after all, what is different is only different from the moment it is considered as such. And whoever considers it must be imbued with the power to classify it as different. This creates the concept that their relationship is a hegemonic relationship, where one will never exist in perfect harmony with the other. There will always be an overlap, but never anything beyond that, and even so, this overlapping relationship will be so subtle that it may be, in many moments, invisible.

Differences and identities are related in a regime of alternation of power. What may be accepted as social identification at one time may be seen as something different from the social process at another. And never as a friendly relationship or one of organic dialecticity. Whenever knowledge is gained with what is identifiable, there will be a concept defined *a priori* and a *fortiori* about what is different. The school entity must promote meetings with the school community and pedagogical team, so that these topics can be brought to the light of reason and addressed in the same way. Excluding those 'considered' different does not make the school 'different'; leaves it the same as the rest of the system.

This is because every 'I' can only exist as a function of the 'other'. The exchange of information helps to build what the man of tomorrow will be, not only in positive identification but also in negative identification; in other words, this would be a process of identity formation based on socio-cognitivism. With this, I infer that the young subject will form his identity, either affirming the values of his society or even denying them.

According to Canen (2001)

The perspective of reproduction, in turn, is informed by a critical-reproductivist approach to education, denouncing that assimilatory process and identifying it throughout formal education. In Brazil, this approach can be related to the fatalism with which reproductive theories were interpreted, in which the school appears as inexorably linked to the reproduction of sociocultural inequalities, leaving no possible space for transformation within the daily routine of educational practices. In this sense, this stance informs a vision of multicultural education reduced to the scope of extra-school movements and spaces, since there is no recognition, within the school, of any perspective of working towards valuing differences and social emancipation (*Id.*, p.211).

However, when society decides to create homogenizing concepts, it ends up excluding the individual from their primeval condition, which is that they have the right to be different and be accepted as such. The right to individuality is subjective and inalienable. When the 1988 Federal Constitution places education as a subjective public right of a social nature, it already

makes it clear that everyone has the right to maintain their subjectivities and to be respected in their most subtle and particular differences.

Identification is what is unconsciously assimilated by the individual thanks to the automatic attitude that leads them to imitate others, especially adults with whom they were emotionally linked in childhood. Thanks to it, today some characters that were previously thought to be inherited are recognized as being precociously acquired. This is what makes a person very similar to those who raised them and to members of their own culture.

The proposal for social inclusion of ex-convicts, in general, is to expand the individual's contact network with modern and erudite, reflective thinking. But to achieve this feat, it is up to the agents promoting this inclusion to devise strategies that simulate everyday situations in the life of the ex-convict when exercising their labor-reflective action.

Under the influence of selective tradition, the formal *corpus* of socio-cultural knowledge produces and reproduces hegemony, causing certain aspects of collective culture to be presented as objective knowledge. It produces standardization and stabilization of learning contexts and forms of consciousness standardized enough to “accept as data of schooling social control, conformism, class distinctions, gender and race, selectivity” (APPLE, 1982, p. 125).

This is the set of norms and values that are implicitly, however, effectively indoctrinated in school institutions and those that are not used to being mentioned in teachers' declarations of aims and objectives. Its perception requires a hermeneutic, almost psychoanalytic analysis of educational processes, highlighting the hidden meanings of what is shown in the declared curricula. It starts from the conviction that all educational discourse is based on implicit assumptions that, broadly speaking, the discourse itself ignores. For this reason, the hidden curriculum reveals itself, especially in the absences, omissions, hierarchies, contradictions and lack of knowledge that the same official curriculum presents and the daily teaching practice that, it is assumed, carries it out; in the same way that a person's unconscious desires are revealed in everyday mistakes (*Ibid.*).

By preserving and practicing attitudes that experts consider to be valid, formal society does nothing more than confer legitimization on the knowledge of certain groups and thus provide qualitatively different forms of inclusion and exclusion of individuals from different social origins, facilitating and complicating and/or preventing their transit and permanence in public life. Formal societies are political spaces shaped, on the one hand, by the strength of social power relations and, on the other, by cultural practice and citizens need to become aware of this game of forces so that, aware of their power of interference, they can act towards to minimize its negative effects; although

The division of society, in which people perform delimited and very specific tasks, causes the human quality of work and life to disappear. The person does not see the situation as a whole, but only sees a small portion of the overall picture, and is thus unable to act without some type of general direction (MILGRAM, 1983, p. 28).

The advances brought about by Taylorist and Fordist methodology transformed common men into even wilder 'beasts' and scientists, who in the infancy of science were excellent intellectuals, were transformed into eminent 'wise idiots' [*idiots svants*]. And this is because they only know how to manipulate a portion of human knowledge reduced every day to more and more microcosmic and microscopic fragments. Therefore, expecting to be able to see a human being, in their entirety, is asking for something far beyond their limited possibilities.

It is very easy to get supporters for summary trials; however, it is impossible to gain supporters for reflection... This is because social ethics dictates that we root out evil. And, they understand, that this cure will occur through annihilation, enclosure, isolation, abandonment of that *which* is 'different'. Many times it was these feelings that took people from relative invisibility to that extreme. This, most of the time, was the only way to tell the world that he existed, a request for someone to notice him, to look at him, even if it was a look of contempt, of hatred, of misery, but to look at him, to make him noticed.

A society that insists on showing itself great through the abusive use of force and imminent domination over others cannot expect its future to be one of peace, considering that its subjects identify with the domination *a fortiori* of the supposedly wisest, most powerful, stronger over others. And these rulers say that they were chosen by God to transmit order to the rest... This is where revolutions are born, because the other side, also believing that it is loved by the same God, has the right to not accept the imposition; what Hegel called a confrontation of rights occurs, as the *root cause* of revolutions.

Abandonment is a feeling that has frightened man since his most primitive era. Being abandoned by his group meant imminent death, as he was an extremely defenseless creature against the natural dangers of the jungle. But, by mere irony, man is the only animal species that abandons its own. Not even wolves do it; When a member of the pack is in such a state of health that it could put the health of the pack at risk, the prophylactic measure taken is his removal, however, two members, in perfect health and combat conditions, are designated to be with the dying person until their complete recovery or until their definitive death.

In the conception of Jaspers (1965),

concerns phenomena, their conditions or potentialities. Man does not identify with any of these aspects, but incorporates them throughout the journey that takes him to himself (JASPERS, 1965, p. 51).

Jaspers means that man is a being produced and inserted in a complex structure; In itself, it is already a very complex ingenuity that is only recognized as a man when he is in his social environment, or better if accepted in a social environment and as an actor and author of his own story. Man is not an end in himself.

SOCIAL ELIGIBILITY AND THE CONSEQUENT LOSS OF VISION FOR THE FUTURE

The life story of the inmates is basically the same, with some reservations. In general, they come from broken homes or are children of fortuitous relationships. They grew up in broken homes, always suffering great deprivation; mainly, affectionate deprivations. Someone can claim that they grew up in a home where they had physical deprivation and yet they did not become a criminal. But I'm not talking about material deprivations, I'm talking about intangible deprivations, things like 'love, affection, affection, understanding, a mother's lap, a father's lap, security [*harmonious balance*] of both.'

Man is not an end in himself. It is a being of continuation, perpetuation and extension. Continued because, at birth, she already brings the genetic baggage of her parents and her education is carried out under the influence of all the cultural baggage of her parents and the environment that surrounds her. Of perpetuation, because he is a being condemned to propagate himself in some way [*currently, the form doesn't matter, but in Antiquity, leaving heirs was an obligation imposed by law under penalty of severe punishment, if ignored or not obeyed*]. In extension, due to the fact that your influence will be [*directly and/or indirectly*] on the people you live with. AND,

This wide road behind us lasts an eternity and this long road before us is a second eternity... These paths are opposites, they oppose each other, and they meet here in this portico. The name of the portico is written above, it is called 'instant'... (NIETZSCHE, 2008, p. 28).

When man separates himself from his group, he becomes animalized, bestialized, brutalized, dehumanized, because exclusion bestializes human beings because man has a desire to be socially accepted, it is not simply a desire, it even becomes anxiety. It is because of this neurotic desire to be accepted by others that he respects social coercion, without question, and

this is why man respected the laws of the city, in Antiquity. He wanted to be someone, he wanted to be seen as such, even if this came at a high cost [*in this case, submission*].

Love is not something innate in man. It was born from contact and the need to form bonds between primitive people because they needed to survive the jungle, other animals and the elements of nature, which were hostile to them, *in extremis*. When human beings form small groups, the need to form more powerful bonds arises, as the fact of being together gives them protection and security and this brings happiness; We didn't even know what this was yet, but it was something good... But note that love, respect, affection, affection are superior, elevated feelings, which only appeared after the emergence of the cerebral cortex, that is, reason. And these are feelings that only have values and implications for man when living in society [*when in contact with his peers*]. What's more, they must be practiced, felt, repeated, so that they can be assimilated and understood by those who are in moral formation [*we cannot forget that man is in constant formation*]. Isolated, all these feelings lose their value, their real need to be and exist for man because there are no limits to respect and no risk of suffering from the loss of these feelings towards him and the company of his peers. But even these sublime feelings are affected by the sociocultural environment.

Human beings can only make plans if they have some perspective for the future. Without this vision of the future, he loses all his security and becomes adrift, at large and at the mercy of luck, chance... Hence we have several cases of people who have floundered along the path of evil, alcohol, addiction, drugs and never leave. Not that it's attractive there, but it's just that human beings seek security above all else and what security does this chaotic system with which we are forced to live (*sic*) offer us?

The worst of all, is when we don't have a VISION, even if we have all the other items (SKILLS + INCENTIVES + RESOURCES + ACTION) the result will be a real CONFUSION [*quid-pro-quo*] (my emphasis), because without vision, It's as if we were traveling along an unknown road without a MAP (...) (PRAZERES, 2008, sp) (*Emphasis in the original*)

Making an analogy with the film *Replicant*, starring Jean Claude Van Damme, in the role of a psychopath and Michael Rooker, in the role of a hard-line police officer, willing to capture the maniac [*at any price, cost and manner*]. Using a fragment of DNA left by the killer at the scene of a crime, the police create a replica of the monster [*a clone, a replicant*] and places him under the care of the police officer so that he can transform him into a serial killer and he spares no effort in beating the *replicant* to the extreme, taking him to the extreme of tolerance. But see, not even the maniac, or any other human being, is born a monster. And the

cell they collect is from a being who was born good and, due to the environment in which he grew up, became evil, therefore, evil would not be in the DNA, but in the person, in the ethical conduct typical of this individual; There were no changes in the genetic structure of this being. And, the strongest scene is when the dog bites the police officer's son and he thinks it was the clone and attacks him with all aggression. The police officer's mother appears and when she sees the *replicant* covered in bruises, she tells her son: "My son, this man is all bruised, he was beaten. If you start treating people like animals, that's what they will turn into" (*Id*).

Brutal societies and brutal situations make the individual see such aggressions as routine and meaningless, causing them to retaliate in the same proportion when opportunities are presented to them. In the case of the film mentioned, the serial killer believed he was practicing an act of kindness, punishing mothers who mistreated their children, given that he had done so in his childhood.

Waiting for a brutalized society to offer conditions for reintegration to ex-convicts in its midst, offering them decent employment opportunities is one way of thinking; but, the reflection of the evil that this individual exposes on everyone, leads her to continue punishing him, as if she were expiating a crime that she carries in her own state of being. Summary trials against everyone is a deplorable situation; but which still persists, although progress has been made in the conditions of respect for social rights guaranteed to all, without distinction, in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948) and ratified in the Federal Constitution of 1988 (BRASIL, 1988).

However, the application of this substantial right still appears to be far from what is necessary to approach social equity. Adolf Hitler (1924) states that, as human beings are subjected to torture and ill-treatment, as well as situations that deprive them of their dignity, the tendency is for them to become cold and indifferent towards situations that, before they caused him indignation. As soon as,

The once diligent man completely abandons his conception of life, little by little, transforming himself into a blind instrument of those who use him only to satisfy the lowest profits [*prostitution*]. Through no fault of his own, he was out of work for so long that once again, once again, it matters little to him. So even when it is not a question of the struggle for the economic rights of the working class, but of the destruction of political, social or cultural values, they will then be, if not enthusiastic about strikes, at least indifferent to them (HITLER, 1924 [2005], p. 15).

It can be inferred from this statement that the cause of violence for many individuals lies in what is learned and experienced during some period of their lives, that is, a social life in which violence is the rule and not the exception. Uncertainty about the future, the lack of public

policies for social inclusion and domestic, urban and social violence increase the social vulnerability and insecurity of many men who stop dreaming and aspiring for a better life.

The man who sees all his neighbors as potential murderers will give up almost anything to be protected from them. He will ask for a strong hand from above; he will become a willing instrument in the oppression of his fellows. He may even allow himself to be turned into an assassin. Society will be atomized into millions of fearful fragments, each reacting to the fear of fantasized individual violence by sponsoring the political conditions for real, large-scale violence.

It appears, therefore, that the social inclusion of ex-prisoners involves dialogue between the parties and the provision of opportunities for them, in addition to an understanding of what is to be and through the provision of public policies aimed at serving the public. in general, with a view to offering social security, preventing the vulnerable class of this country, which are young people, from being led into the world of crime as a resource for valuing the *status quo* .

CONCLUSION

The issue of social inclusion of ex-prisoners is a controversial, complex subject and, although it has been discussed on a wide scale, the depth of the topic has not gone beyond the shallow and superficial. What is under discussion, in this case, is not the individual who needs re-entry, but the social situation that does not change its concepts and values, in order to have a less unfair community, since, in many cases, it is She herself is the one who pushes the majority of individuals in delinquent situations into this state, as the ultimate aim of survival in a hostile and unbalanced world, in every sense.

What comes into question is the condition that, once the sentence to which he was sentenced had been carried out, the judgment had already been given and there would no longer be any need to be punished, now by an abstract court that uses an also abstract form for this, which is the exclusion and consequent marginalization of beings, removing them from the possibility of a life with dignity. In this case, the person who needs changes is not the ex-convict; but, the society that denies him due reception.

This condition to which he is subjected, *a fortiori* , causes him to lose his vision of the future, already deteriorated even before he was condemned, because claiming that everyone must have a perspective on life, this works very well when you are under the protection of individuals who welcome him and in a society that respects him. Put on the sidelines of life from an early age, what we have is, in many cases, the path of violence as the ultimate aim of

survival, causing many of these individuals, once released, to seek delinquency as a way to return to prison, where they do not lack the basics for existence, such as bed, food, water and recognition from their peers.

REFERENCES

APPLE, Michael . *Ideology and Curriculum*. São Paulo: Editora Brasiliense, 1982.

BETTELHEIM, Bruno. *The Psychoanalysis of Fairy Tales*. 3. Ed. São Paulo: Editora Paz e Terra, 1980.

Id. . A Life for Your Son. Rio de Janeiro: Campus, 1988. Chapter 20: Unconscious Sources, Concrete Achievements.

BORGES, Patrícia Ferreira Bianchini. *School x Youth*. Available at: meuartigo.brasilecola.com/educacao/escola-x-juventude.htm. Accessed on 10/26/2023.

BRAZIL. Constitution (1988). *Constitution of the Federative Republic of Brazil*. Brasília: Federal Senate, 1988.

CANEN, Ana. *Cultural Universes and Teaching Representations: Subsidies for Teacher Training for Cultural Diversity*. Rio de Janeiro: Education & Society, year XXII, nº 77. December/2001.

FERNANDES, Domingos (2005/2009) Assessment of learning in Portugal: research and activity theory. Institute of Education at the University of Lisbon, Portugal - *Sísifo/Revista de Ciências da Educação* - nº 9 (May/Aug 09 ISSN 1646-4990).

FOUCAULT, Michel. *Discipline and Punish: Birth of Prisons*. 29. Ed. Rio de Janeiro: Vozes, 2004.

Id .. The archeology of Knowledge. 7. Ed. Rio de Janeiro: Forense Universitária, 2005.

GRAMSCI, Antonio. *Intellectuals and the organization's culture*. 38. Ed. São Paulo: Círculo do Livro SA, 1996.

HITLER, ADOLF. *My fight*. 1st part. Chapter II: Years of Learning and Suffering in Vienna. Munich [Germany], 1924 [2005]. If

JASPERS, Karl. *Introduction to Philosophical Thought*. 3. Ed. São Paulo: Cultrix, 1965, p. 50-51. Chapter IV: The Man.

LAVILLE, Christian; DIONNE, Jean. *The construction of knowledge : research methodology manual in human sciences*. Porto Alegre: Artmed; Belo Horizonte: UFMG, 1999.

MOSCOVICI, S. *Social representations: investigations in social psychology*. Rio de Janeiro, Voices, 2003.

MULLAHY, Patrick. *Oedipus: Myth and Complex – A Critique of Psychoanalytic Theory*. 3. Ed. Rio de Janeiro: Zahar Editores, 1975. Chapter 5: The Theories of Alfred Adler.

NIETZSCHE, Friedrich Wilhelm. *Thus Spoke Zarathustra*. São Paulo: Escala, 2006.

Id. . *Beyond Good and Evil*. São Paulo: Martin Claret, 2004.

Id. . *On the Utility and Inconvenience of History for Life*. São Paulo: Escala, 2008.

ORLANDI, Eni P. *Discourse Analysis: principles & procedures*. 6. Ed. São Paulo: Pontes, 2005.

PAPINI, Raiani. *Life imprisonment: Prejudice prevents former inmates from entering society*. In : O EstadoRJ.com.br, 2012.

PIOVESAN, F. *Human Rights Themes*. 3. Ed. São Paulo: Ed. Saraiva (Legal), 2009.

PIOVESAN, Flávia; SOUZA, Douglas Martins de. *Legal Order and Ethnic-Racial Equality*. São Paulo: Lúmen Júris, 2006.

PLAYFAIR, Giles; SINGTON, Derrick. *Prison does not cure, it corrupts*. São Paulo: Ibrasa, 1969.

PLEASURES, Dorieldo Luís dos. *Electronic Correspondence Sent to the Author*, on 09/12/2008.

SILVA, Tomaz Tadeu da. *The social production of identity and difference*. Available at: ccs.ufpel.edu.br/.../a-producao-social-da-identidade-e-da-diference.p... Accessed on 04/26/2012.

SOUZA, Sérgio Rodrigues de. *Ethics and Its Implications in the Formation of the Human Condition*. Mutum: Expresso Gráfica, 2012.

Id. . *The Justice League on the Divan*. Mutum: Expresso Gráfica, 2012.

VASCONCELOS, MJE *Systemic Thinking: The new paradigm of Science*. Campinas: Papyrus, 2002

VICTORA, CG; Knauth DR, Hassen MNA *Qualitative health research: an introduction to the topic* . Porto Alegre: Editorial Tome; 2000.

ZIMBARDO, Phillip. *The Stanford Prison Experiment*. Stanford University, 1971.